

ether solution with Pd-charcoal in an atmosphere of hydrogen to yield a single compound, stigmast-8(14)-en-3 β -yl acetate, m.p. 115° (lit⁶ m.p. 115°) (Found: C, 81.36; H, 11.54. C₃₁H₄₈O₂ calcd. C, 81.52; H, 11.48%) [α]_D +20°; δ 2.03 (3H,s), 4.7 (1H,t) and no olefinic proton. *m/z* 456 (M⁺, 100%), 441, 396 and 381.

Solid A: Solid B on oxidation with chromium trioxide-pyridine complex⁷ yielded the less polar component Solid A, m.p. 168-170°; [α]_D +36.7° which was identical (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with a sample of Solid A from natural source. Hence Solid A was a mixture of stigmasta-7,22-dien-3-one⁸ and stigmast-7-en-3-one⁹.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to M/s East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta for the award of a Research Scholarship to one of them (S.D.).

References

1. "The Wealth of India: Raw Materials", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1952, Vol. III, p. 185.
2. F. BOHLMANN and C. ZDERO, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 2465.
3. D. H. R. BARTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 813; T. K. DEVON and A. I. SCOTT, "Handbook of Naturally Occurring Compounds", Academic Press, New York, 1972, Vol II, p. 400.
4. J. W. CLARK-LEWIS and I. DAINIS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 1961 and references cited therein.
5. E. FERNHOLZ and W. L. RUGH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2341.
6. H. A. SCHUETTE and W. E. LINK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4192.
7. G. I. POOS, G. E. ARTH, R. E. BEYLER and L. H. SARETT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 425.
8. S. KUWADA and S. YOSIKI, *J. Pharm. Soc. Jpn.*, 1940, 60, 85 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1940, 34, 5088).
9. W. SUCROW and A. REIMERDES, *Z. Naturwissen.*, 1968, 42.

Spectrophotometric Study of Reaction Between Iron(III) and 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime

K. S. SANTHA LAKSHMI, R. RAGHAVA NAIDU*
and
V. R. KRISHNAN

Department of Chemistry, School of Mathematical and Physical Sciences, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati-517 502

Manuscript received 25 October 1983, revised 26 June 1984, accepted 19 January 1985

SEVERAL oximes¹⁻¹¹ have been proposed for the colorimetric determination of iron(III), but in most of the cases the color was not stable for sufficiently longer periods because of the dissociation of the complexes. We have now found that 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime develops an intense forest-green color with iron(III) at pH 2.3-2.7 and the reaction is highly sensitive and selective. The

sensitivity according to Sandell's method¹² is 27.9 ng cm⁻², and as determined by Feigl's method¹³ the limits of identification and dilution are found to be 100 ng and 1.1 × 10⁶, respectively. The color is stable for about six hours and, therefore, a detailed spectrophotometric investigation of the complex was carried out.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime was prepared according to the procedure described by Vogel¹⁴. Ferric alum (A.R., B.D.H.) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and standardised by volumetric method¹⁵.

A Toshniwal CLO/O2A conductivity bridge, an Elico 820A pH meter and a Toshniwal RLO2 spectrophotometer were employed for conductance, pH and absorbance measurements, respectively.

Procedure: An aliquot of Fe^{III} solution containing not more than 24 ppm of iron was treated with 4 ml of 0.1 per cent solution of oxime at room temperature. The pH was adjusted to 2.5 and the volume made up to 50 ml. The absorbance of the iron complex was measured at 450 nm with the reagent of the same concentration as the blank. The concentration of iron was deduced from a standard calibration curve obtained under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Iron(III) complex exhibits maximum absorption at 450 nm at which the reagent, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime has no absorption. Any excess reagent has no effect on the absorbance of the complex. The complex obeys Beer's law in the range 6-24 ppm of iron(III). The sensitivity according to Sandell's definition is 27.9 ng cm⁻² at 450 nm for an absorbance of 0.001 with a molar absorptivity of 0.2 × 10³ l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Job's method of continuous variation^{16,17}, slope ratio¹⁸, mole ratio¹⁹ and Asmus methods²⁰ showed that the ratio of metal to ligand in the complex is 1 : 1. The study of the isobestic point (Fig. 1) obtained by plotting the optical densities of the complex against the wavelength at various pH values (2.5-10.5) indicated that during the pH range 2.5-4.5 the absorption curves do not pass through the isobestic point and hence, a single complex was present, while an isobestic point exists in the pH 5.5-10.5 at a wavelength 415 nm and an optical density of 0.085 showing the presence of a mixture of complexes.

The iron-naphthaldoxime complex could be readily extracted into nitrobenzene. The conductance of pure nitrobenzene as well as the iron complex in this solvent was found to be 5 × 10⁻⁴ Ω⁻¹. This clearly shows that the complex is a non-electrolyte. One of the most conspicuous features of ferric iron in aqueous solution is its tendency to hydrolyse. In the pH range 2-3 iron may be present

Fig. 1. Plot of optical density vs wavelength of iron-2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime complex at various pH values.

as $[\text{Fe}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$. The reagent under investigation is a bidentate uninegative ligand. It forms a 1:1 complex with iron replacing two water molecules from the coordination sphere. It is also known from the conductance measurements that the complex is neutral, hence, assuming that iron in the complex is tripositive, one charge being neutralised by the oxime and the other two charges by the anionic ligands present in the medium, possibly OH^- , the formula of the complex is suggested as $[\text{FeL}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{OH})_2]$.

Interferences: The interference of various ions associated with iron(III) in its ores, alloys, living systems and precipitated with it in analysis on the absorbancy of iron complex was studied. 10 ppm/50 ml of iron(III) in each case was treated with the reagent (4 ml, 0.1%) and known variable amounts of other ion. The pH was adjusted to 2.5 and optical densities were measured. Na and K ions have no effect on the absorbancy even when each ion was present upto 400 ppm. Mg^{2+} (100 ppm), Ca^{2+} (100 ppm), Sn^{2+} (90 ppm), Be^{2+} (100 ppm), Zn^{2+} (100 ppm), Mn^{2+} (85 ppm), U^{10}O_8 (60 ppm), Cr^{3+} (50 ppm), Sb^{3+} (50 ppm), As^{3+} (60 ppm), Ti^{4+} (50 ppm), Th^{4+} (55 ppm), Co^{2+} (7 ppm), Mo^{6+} (7 ppm), W^{6+} (7 ppm), Bi^{3+} (7 ppm), and V^{5+} (10 ppm) ions cause not more than 0.05% error in the determination of 10 ppm of iron when present in the amounts shown in brackets. Cu^{2+} and Zr^{4+} ions interfered by forming precipitates with the reagent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of a Teacher Fellowship to one of them (K.S.S.L.).

References

1. HOWE and MELLON, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1940, 448.
2. K. NEELAKANTAM and SITARAMAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1945, 14, 320.
3. G. RAJA REDDY, S. G. KADARMANDALGI and A. S. R. MURTHY, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1964, 59, 159.

4. K. ADINARAYANA REDDY, Ph.D. Thesis, S. V. University, 1973.
5. F. TRUSELL and H. DIEHL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 1978.
6. D. K. BANERJEE and K. K. TRIPATHI, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 1196.
7. Z. MARCZENKO and KASIURA, *Chem. Anal.*, 1961, 6, 37.
8. A. TAKESHI and V. KEIHEL, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1966, 39, 2400.
9. M. H. GANDHI, DESAI and MAHENDRA, *Chem. Anal.*, 1968, 50, 167.
10. R. N. MERCHANT and D. N. PATKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 531.
11. J. SINGH and S. P. GUPTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 612.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New York, 1959.
13. F. FEIGL, "Qualitative Analysis by Spot Tests (Inorganic Applications)", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1954, p. 4.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1968, p. 171.
15. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1961, p. 309.
16. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1925, 9, 113.
17. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
18. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
19. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Soc. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
20. A. ASMUS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 178, 104.
21. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 4th. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1980.

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ruthenium(III) Using 6-Amino-5-nitroso-2,4-pyrimidinediol and Pyridine

R. S. SINDHU

Chemistry Department, M. S. College, Saharanpur-247 001

and

R. P. SINGH

Chemistry Department, Delhi University, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 8 March 1984, accepted 8 November 1984

A number of pyrimidine derivatives have been recently introduced as reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of different matters¹. Ruthenium has been estimated spectrophotometrically with 6-amino-5-nitroso-2,4-pyrimidinediol² (6-ANP). The idea that the formation of the ternary complex can lead to better sensitivity than binary complex has motivated us to carry out its determination with 6-ANP and pyridine.

Experimental

The stock solution of Ru^{3+} was prepared by dissolving $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Koch Light, U.K.) in 1.0 N HCl. Solutions of primary ligand, 6-ANP (monosodium salt) and secondary ligand, pyridine were prepared in 0.1 N HCl. The pH of the solutions were adjusted with acetate buffer and dilute solutions of HCl and NaOH. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Double-distilled water was used throughout the work.